

PRACTICAL FEATURES OF FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE ECOSYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Annotation: *This article shows that the strategy of introduction of digital technologies in the banking practice of our country and the peculiarities of the formation of an innovative ecosystem in commercial banks, based on the experience of leading banks in the world.*

Keywords: *innovations in banking, innovative ecosystem of the bank, models, artificial intelligence.*

Introduction

It is clear that the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2021 "On measures to create conditions for the accelerated introduction of artificial intelligence technologies" PP-4996 the task of creating a local ecosystem of innovative developments in the field of stimulating artificial intelligence was identified. This task, in our opinion, indicates the need to recognize the formation of an innovative ecosystem in commercial banks as one of the current areas of development.

Today, despite the recognition of financial stability as a priority in the development strategy of banks, the automation of business processes, expanding the use of electronic platforms to offer customers banking services and products, the usage of "cloud technology" in management decision-making is a factor that strengthens, expands the customer and resource base. Based on the above and the practice of leading foreign banks, we try to study the peculiarities of the innovative ecosystem in the banking sector of our country.

The main part.

First of all, it should be noted that the formation of an innovative ecosystem requires large and long-term investments. Not all innovative projects that have been (or are being implemented) at the same time will always produce the desired effect (income). The magnitude of these and other levels of risk requires an analysis of the financial capacity of banks. According to the rating company Standard & Poor's, by the end of 2020, the volume of assets accumulated in the world's 10 largest banks will reach 35 trillion. 97 billion USD, the deposit base is 22 trillion. 644

billion USD, the amount of private capital is 2 trillion. 713.5 mln. USD. By 2020, the world's gross domestic product at purchasing power parity will reach 132 trillion. 647 billion Was equal to USD. Thus, the assets of the top ten banks accounted for 26.5% of GDP, the volume of attracted deposits - 17.1% and the volume of capital - 2.1%. It should be noted that despite the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic, by the end of 2020, the total assets of these banks will be in France (GDP - 3,115 billion US dollars), Germany (GDP - 4,469 billion US dollars), India (GDP - 8). 907 billion US dollars). If we look at the generalized financial indicators of the banking sector of Uzbekistan, we can see that by the end of 2020, bank assets will account for 61.3% of GDP, attracted deposits - 19.8%, and bank capital - 10.1%

These data suggest that commercial banks can form their own directly affected or indirectly controlled ecosystems without compromising the organizational structure, without compromising the requirements of the law.

According to the research, the following three basic models of innovation organization are used in the practice of the world's largest banks, such as Bank of America (USA), BNP Paribas (France), Sber Group (Russia):

The first model is the formation of an internal innovation ecosystem by supporting the innovative activities of bank employees. This model, in addition to ensuring the security of information and operations, increases the level of protection of the bank from changes and risks in the external technological environment. Examples include Bank of America Mobile Banking's Erica and Zelle virtual platforms and virtual channels created at the bank.

The second model is to meet the demand for innovative developments through the establishment of subsidiaries and other types of bank-controlled companies and startups specializing in innovative activities. This model serves to expand the scope of innovative opportunities through various forms of partnerships with subsidiaries and startups, as well as higher education institutions and other startups. BNP Paribas 'Cardif Insurance subsidiary and SMART Derivatives electronic platform can be cited as a result of the application of the model.

The third model is to gain an innovative priority by gradually transforming banking activities into a technology company. The SberX division of the Sber Group and research laboratories such as Robotics, Blockchain, Artificial Intelligence work in this direction.

The analysis of the processes of organizing innovative activities in the banking sector of the country allows us to note a number of specific features:

The proliferation of financial technologies and the growing demand for them in the most important customer segments, as well as the growing focus on converting closed systems (especially IABTs) used in commercial banks to open

electronic platforms to relatively reduce investment in basic infrastructure and technological assets. Despite the high level of security risk, the introduction of software application interfaces (APIs) to open the functions of internal information systems to external users and establish communication channels with them has led to the expansion of corporate and mobile banking capabilities;

security of information and operations, creation of Data Warehouse and banking business analysis system, application of SubTech and RegTech technologies in banking regulation, introduction of IFRS 9 requirements to improve corporate governance, SAP BW and SAP BO systems in assessing potential losses on bank assets application, etc. have an impact on the organization of innovation processes in commercial banks.

Conclusions and suggestions

The conducted research allows to note the following features:

Firstly, the formation of an innovative ecosystem directly or indirectly controlled by commercial banks with large financial capabilities will turn them into drivers of innovative development not only in fintex, but also in Big data, API, biometrics, artificial intelligence and other areas.

Secondly, models of innovation activity depend on the economic policy pursued in the country, strategic goals of banking development, availability of highly qualified specialists and technological base, as well as other macro and micro level factors that influence the scale and forms of innovation ecosystem formation.

Thirdly, the entry of bigtech companies, payment systems and other high-tech companies into the traditional banking services market will make innovative activity in banks a key tool in the fight against competition and strengthening market position.

Based on these features, the following proposals and recommendations for the formation of an innovative ecosystem of banks were developed:

- In order to reduce the level of operational risks, it is necessary to integrate into the automated banking systems the software of IT companies (in particular, the scoring system) and QQAT (automated decision-making systems), which can be directly influenced only by banks;

- It is expedient to establish in each commercial bank banking divisions specializing in the creation of innovative technologies;

- To support and encourage the innovative activities of bank employees, it is necessary to include in the reward system a system of indicators related to innovative activities.

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